

XROTOR

X-shaped Radical Offshore Wind Turbine for Overall Cost of Energy Reduction

D8.2

X-Rotor Development Workshop

 <https://xrotor-project.eu>

 @XROTORProject

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About X-ROTOR

X-ROTOR: “X-shaped Radical Offshore wind Turbine for Overall cost of energy Reduction” is a Horizon 2020 funded project which aims to develop a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept.

The X-ROTOR project is led by University of Strathclyde (UK) in partnership with Norwegian University of Science and Technology (Norway), Delft University of Technology (Netherlands), University College Cork (Ireland), Fundacion Cener National Renewable Energy Centre (Spain) and GE Renovables España (Spain).

As the effects of climate change are becoming ever more visible, Europe has raised its target for the amount of energy it consumes from renewable sources from the previous goal of 27% to 32% by 2030. Offshore wind energy can play a key role in achieving the EU target and contribute to the required 40% reduction in CO₂ emissions. However, to achieve the previously mentioned targets the cost of offshore wind must be reduced. The X-ROTOR concept provides a direct route to drastically reducing both capital and operating costs of energy from offshore wind.

The project runs for three years from January 2021, during which time, the concept will be developed through a holistic consideration of technical, cost, environmental and socio-economic impact aspects.

If proven feasible, X-ROTOR will, as a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept, create new opportunities for the European wind energy industry and play an important role maintaining the EU’s position as global technological leader in renewable energy, reducing greenhouse gas emissions and decarbonising the EU economy.

For more information see <https://xrotor-project.eu>

1 Description of the deliverable and its purpose

Annual workshop delivered to obtain industrial input on project development. This deliverable will be considered successfully complete once the workshop is held each year. The workshop report will be delivered as part of deliverable 8.6.

2 D8.2 Note on X-Rotor Development Workshop

This note for deliverable D8.2 is to confirm that the annual workshop to obtain industrial input on project development was delivered each year of the XROTOR project. The industrial input was provided by GE and is detailed in D8.6. A milestone would have been more suitable for this deliverable as it fully overlaps with D8.6 report and D8.2 is present in the Eu Portal SyGMA as “Other” rather than a “Report”.

Please see the report from D8.6 for further details on each workshop including, description, location, attendees, agenda etc.